

Studies in 1-Aza-1,3-butadienes: Ultraviolet Spectral Studies of Conjugated Azomethines

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Some new open-chain conjugated azomethines have been synthesized in high yields and their ultraviolet absorption spectra recorded. A strong absorption band at ~280 nm. has been found to be of diagnostic value for the azomethine linkage.

LITTLE is known about the electronic spectra of the $-C=N-$ group in a purely aliphatic environment. The azomethine, $CH_3CH=NC_3H_7$,¹ gives a strong diffuse band centred at about 1700 Å ($\epsilon = 8000$). It has been found² that the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition lies at 2100 Å if the substituents in the $-C=N-$ group are aliphatic, at 2500 if it is vinylic and at 2900 if it is benzenoid. In the aromatic series spectrum of benzalaniline has been compared with those of stilbene and azobenzene³. Solvent effects due to hydrogen-bonding have also been noted in *N*-salicylidene alkylanilines⁴. Non-coplanarity of the azomethine molecule has been concluded in another study⁵. Ultraviolet spectra of aromatic Schiff bases⁶ and linearly conjugated systems^{7,8} have also been recorded. But no systematic study of ultra-violet spectra appears to have been reported in the case of conjugated imines. An attempt has therefore been made here to assign the band position to the conjugated azomethine linkage and to note the effect of a strongly electron-withdrawing nitro group in the ortho position of the C-phenyl in conjugation with an azomethine group.

So, twelve different 1-aza-1,3-butadienes, having various groups like $-CH_3$, $-OH$, $-OCH_3$, $-OC_2H_5$, $-Cl$, $-Br$, $-NO_2$ in the ortho, meta and para positions of the *N*-phenyl ring have been prepared by condensing *o*-nitrocinnamaldehyde with substituted anilines.

o-Nitrocinnamaldehyde⁹ was obtained by the nitration of redistilled cinnamaldehyde in acetic anhydride (BDH) using nitric acid (AR) in glacial acetic acid as the nitrating agent. The product was recrystallized from 95% ethyl alcohol and used subsequently.

From this study, it is obvious that some absorption bands (band II at 235 nm and band II at 335 nm) show a bathochromic shift to a longer wave-length as a result of *N*-phenyl substitution, while other bands (band I at 213 nm and band III at 281 nm) usually remain unaffected. A shoulder appears at 233-250 nm as a result of substitution by an electron-donating group, with a red shift as the electron-donating capacity increases. These observations indicate that the bands sensitive to substitution correspond to electronic transitions involving the *N*-phenyl ring and the bands that remain unaffected correspond to transitions involving the aldehydic portion of the molecule. The above observations support the non-coplanar structure of the molecule, though it may also indicate a weak interaction between the aromatic rings of the molecule.

The spectrum of 1-phenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1,3-butadiene is interpreted in terms of aniline and aldehyde non-interacting moieties.

Band I (213 nm) is sensitive to C-phenyl substitution as is shown by the fact that *o*-nitro substitution and conjugation to a $-CH=CH-$ group of the phenyl ring in the aldehyde moiety of the molecule gives a blue shift as compared to benzalaniline spectrum. So this band may be taken as the perturbed ${}^1B_{2u}$ band of the aldehyde portion of the molecule.

Band II (235 nm) is found to be sensitive to *N*-phenyl substitution as is evident from the Table

No. 2 and may thus be considered as a charge-transfer band of the aniline part of the molecule. This band in aniline has appreciable local-excited-state character corresponding to a benzene ${}^1B_{1u}$ type-state. This band, which appears as a shoulder in some azome-

TABLE 1. SYNTHESIS OF 1-AZA-1,3-BUTADIENES ($o\text{-NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{X}$)

Sl. No.	X=	Reaction time	M.P.* °C	Yield %	Solvent of recrystallization	Mol. Formula	Elemental Analysis	
							Found N%	Calculated N%
1.	-H	30 mts.	103	80	95% ethanol	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$	11.31	11.11
2.	$o\text{-CH}_3$	-do-	102	75	-do-	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$	10.56	10.53
3.	$p\text{-CH}_3$	20 mts.	100	94	-do-	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$	10.20	10.53
4.	$p\text{-OCH}_3$	25-30 mts.	95-96	96	-do-	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	9.72	9.53
5.	$p\text{-OC}_2\text{H}_5$	-do-	78	95	-do-	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	9.64	9.46
6.	$o\text{-OH}$	30 mts.	114	80	-do-	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	10.20	10.44
7.	$p\text{-OH}$	60 mts.	193-194	85	boiling methanol	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	10.53	10.44
8.	$m\text{-Cl}$	45 mts.	110	86	95% ethanol	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$	9.58	9.77
9.	$p\text{-Cl}$	60 mts.	118	80	-do-	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$	9.69	9.77
10.	$p\text{-Br}$	90 mts.	110-111	80	-do-	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Br}$	8.62	8.47
11.	$m\text{-NO}_2$	4 hrs.	172-173	50	Acetic acid	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$	13.77	14.15
12.	$p\text{-NO}_2$	3 hrs.	190-191	55	-do-	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$	14.64	14.15

* The melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE 2. ULTRAVIOLET ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF 1-AZA-1, 3-BUTADIENES ($o\text{-NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}:\text{CHCH}:\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{X}$).

Sl.No.	X=	Band I		Band II		Band III		Band IV	
		$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ nm (log ϵ)		$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ nm (log ϵ)		$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ nm (log ϵ)		$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ nm (log ϵ)	
1.	-H	213	(4.09)	235	(4.23)	281	(4.59)	335	(4.33)
2.	$o\text{-CH}_3$	210	(3.36)	—	—	278	(3.40)	337.5	(3.08)
3.	$p\text{-CH}_3$	207.5	(4.19)	233	(4.19)	281	(4.47)	345	(4.36)
4.	$p\text{-OCH}_3$	210	(4.29)	250	(4.29)	284	(4.38)	361	(4.31)
5.	$p\text{-OC}_2\text{H}_5$	210	(4.36)	249	(4.37)	285	(4.46)	361	(4.40)
6.	$o\text{OH}$	209.5	(4.54)	240	(4.33)	280	(4.79)	369	(3.84)
7.	$p\text{-OH}$	209	(4.25)	251	(4.24)	285	(4.32)	365	(4.26)
8.	$m\text{-Cl}$	211	(3.38)	—	—	281	(3.36)	330	(3.15)
9.	$p\text{-Cl}$	212	(4.21)	—	—	281	(4.37)	336	(4.21)
10.	$p\text{-Br}$	210	(4.23)	—	—	284	(4.32)	340	(4.22)
11.	$m\text{-NO}_2$	—	—	—	—	268	(5.54)	—	—
12.	$p\text{-NO}_2$	212.5	(4.57)	230	(4.53)	—	—	375	(4.63)

thines with electron-donating substituents in N-phenyl ring of the molecule may also be taken as corresponding to the third electronic transition-state of aniline involving an electronic-state that too possesses mixed charge-transfer and locally-excited characters. Thus a clear distinction between a locally-excited and a charge-transfer transition may not be valid (when configurational interaction is present).

Band III (281 nm) is relatively insensitive to N-phenyl substitution but seems to be sensitive to C-phenyl substitution as o -nitro substitution and conjugation with a $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ group give a red shift corresponding to the 262 nm band of benzaldehyde. This corresponds to a transition to a charge-transfer state in which the C-phenyl group acts as an electron-donor and the azomethine group as an electron-acceptor. This is the band, which can be used to identify the azomethine linkage as is evidenced by the fact that this band completely

disappears on reduction of the azomethine group with sodium borohydride¹⁰ and the shoulder at ~ 250 nm becomes the prominent band in this region.

Band IV (335 nm) is sensitive to N-phenyl substitution and may correspond to a transition, to a benzene ${}^1\text{B}_{2u}$ type-state in the aniline part of the molecule. A transition to a benzene ${}^1\text{B}_{2u}$ type-state in the aldehydic moiety is hidden under the more intense transitions as it is expected to be of lower intensity and to adsorb at 290 nm.

Intramolecular hydrogen-bonding seems to occur in the case of 1- o -hydroxyphenyl-4- o -nitrophenyl-1-aza-1, 3-butadiene as a shift of 11 nm is observed in the case of band II. This band is in the form of

a shoulder and is hidden under the more intense transitions in the case of azomethines with electron-withdrawing substituents in the N-phenyl ring of the molecule. Strong electron-withdrawing effect of *m*-nitro substitution in the N-phenyl ring manifests itself in the spectrum of 1-*m*-nitrophenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1, 3-butadiene. In this case a high intensity band at 268 nm is observed and all the other bands are hidden under these more intense transitions. Similar effect, but to a lesser extent, is shown in the spectrum of *p*-nitro substituted product. Here the band at 284 nm is not observable due to other stronger transitions.

Experimental

The ultraviolet absorption spectra of these imines has been recorded in methanol (BDH) on a manually operated spectrophotometer (Hilger-Watts Model H-700) using silica cells.

Synthesis of 1-p-Tolyl-4-o-Nitrophenyl-1-Aza-1,3-butadiene :

To a hot ethanolic solution of *o*-nitrocinnamaldehyde (1.77 g., 0.01 mole) in a 100 ml. conical flask, was added an ethanolic solution of *p*-toluidine (1.07 g., 0.01 mole). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 15 min when crystallization of 1-*p*-tolyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1, 3-butadiene started. At the completion of the crystallization, the contents were filtered at the suction and the product was recrystallized from hot ethanol to give glistening yellow plates, m.p. 100°, yield 2.49 g. (94%). (Found : N, 10.20 required for C₁₆H₁₄N₂O₂ : N, 10.53%). λ_{max}^{MeOH} 281 nm (log ϵ 4.46).

The other azabutadienes were synthesized by gently refluxing equimolar amounts of freshly recrystallized *o*-nitrocinnamaldehyde and the respective aniline taken in sodium dried benzene using a 'Dean and Stark' water separator. *o*-Nitrocinnamaldehyde was obtained by the nitration of freshly distilled cinnamaldehyde in acetic anhydride (BDH) using nitric acid (AR) in glacial acetic acid as the nitrating agent⁹ at 0°-5°.

A typical method for this condensation is given below :

Synthesis of 1-Phenyl-4-o-Nitrophenyl-1-Aza-1, 3-butadiene :

o-Nitrocinnamaldehyde (1.77 g., 0.01 mole) was taken in a 100 ml., standard joint (B-24) R.B. flask. To it was added dry (BDH) benzene (50 ml.), and freshly distilled aniline (0.91 ml., 0.01 mole). The mixture was gently refluxed using a 'Dean and Stark' water-separator. The reaction was complete within 30 min as indicated by the collection of the requisite amount of water. The excess of the solvent was then pulled off under vacuo and the contents were cooled in an ice-bath. The crude product was filtered at the pump and recrystallization from ethanol yielded bright yellow needles m.p. 103°, yield 2.0 g (80%). (Found : C, 71.40; H, 4.81; N, 11.31; require for C₁₅H₁₂N₂O₂ : C, 71.48; H, 4.80; N, 11.11%). ν_{max}^{KBr} (cm⁻¹) 1610, s(C = N); 1509, 1340, s(NO₂) and 978, s(CH = CH, trans). λ_{max}^{MeOH} 281 nm (log ϵ 4.59).

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